

International Monitoring Operation
*Project for the Support to the Process of Temporary
Re-evaluation of Judges and Prosecutors in Albania*

Ref. No: 16

Tirana, 17 January 2022

From: IMO International Observers

To: [REDACTED]
Chair of the Independent Qualification Commission
Rruga e Kavajes No. 4
Tirana
Albania

Subject: **Financial Contribution of [REDACTED] to IQC's 'Strategy Meeting' in Vlora on 29 and 30 September 2021**

Dear [REDACTED]

The International Observers were made aware of the following facts:

Following media reports on a third-party financing of the above indicated IQC event, IMO was asking the IQC for information on this issue.

According to the information received, the IQC asked the insurance company [REDACTED] – making express reference to an insurance contract between IQC and [REDACTED] – for a financial contribution in the form of sponsorship for the above indicated IQC event.

On the basis of this request, a contract qualified as “sponsorship agreement” between IQC and [REDACTED] was concluded on 14 June 2021. According to this agreement, [REDACTED] undertook to ‘sponsor’ this event with EUR 3.000,00, to be used for the travel and accommodation of IQC staff and the conference room for the workshop. According to IMO’s information, this contract has been executed as foreseen in the contract.

The above-mentioned circumstances have important legal and practical implications.

In fact, art. 1 of law no. 7892, dated 21.12.1994 “On Sponsorships” provides that “this law regulates financial aid – hereinunder referred to as sponsorships – of social and public activities

where are included humanitarian, cultural and artistic, sports, educative, education, ecological, literature, scientific and encyclopedic and press publishing.” According to the above-mentioned law, the activity must thus fall under one of the above categories to be subject of the Law. Article 2 specifically provides that “only the activities under article 1 – that are carried out by entities, institutions, NGOs and organizations recognized by law and registered as legal entities – can be sponsored.” It does not seem, therefore, that the law allows the sponsorship of activities similar to the one in question here.

The International Observers are well aware that Art. 19 Vetting Law allows secondary incomes for the re-evaluation bodies. Specifically, article 19 para 4 provides that “the institutions shall have the right to use secondary incomes, gained by international projects, donations and their publications.”

However, one fundamental problematic issue persists.

It appears, in fact, highly inappropriate for a vetting institution to solicit donations from private entities,

The above is harmful for the credibility and reputation of IQC.

In light of the above, the International Observers:

- express their contrariety to the initiative described above
- urge the IQC to refrain from similar initiatives in the future
- invite the IQC, should any dubious situations arise in the future, to preemptively consult with the International Observers.

The International Observers remain committed to support the Independent Qualification Commission in the exercise of its mandate.

Sincerely yours, on behalf of the International Observers

International Observers

